

A New Synthesis of *dl*-Cryptone

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A new synthesis of *dl*-cryptone has been accomplished.

Cryptone¹ (IV) is an unsaturated ketone and occurs in nature both in the *laevo* as well as in the *dextro* form.

The earlier approaches² to its synthesis involve the prior production of the $\beta\gamma$ -unsaturated cyclic ketone from *p*-isopropylanisole by the Birch reduction and this is subsequently rearranged to the $\alpha\beta$ -isomer. This isomerisation is, however, not a spontaneous process³.

The present scheme offers a new approach which can result only in the $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated ketonic system and thus renders this synthesis free of the ambiguity associated with earlier attempts.

Ethyl γ -acetyl- δ -methylcaproate (I), obtained by cyanoethylating ethyl α -isopropylacetoacetate and subsequent ketonic hydrolysis and esterification, was cyclised with sodium ethoxide to 4-isopropylcyclohexan-1,3-dione (II).

1. Chan *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 1366; Berry *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1937, 1448; Cook and Macbeth, *ibid.*, 1938, 1408; Wichaus and Striegler, *Schimmel Reports*, 1937, p. 91.
2. Bhati, *Curr. Sci.*, 1952, 21, 314; Soffer and Jevnik, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 70, 1003; Sukh Dev, *this Journal*, 1956, 33, 541.
3. Birch, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 593; Wildman *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 75, 1912.

The diketone (II) on being treated with butanol¹ in benzene in presence of catalytic amount of *p*-toluenesulphonic acid, produced 2-isopropyl-5-isobutoxycyclohex-5-enone⁴ (III) in 70% yield. The orientation in the enolic ether (III) is based on the considerations of stereointeractions involving the isopropyl and isobutoxy groups.⁵

The ketone (III) on reduction with lithium aluminium hydride and subsequent treatment with 10% sulphuric acid afforded *dl*-cryptone⁶.

EXPERIMENTAL

Ethyl γ -Acetyl- δ -methylcaproate (I).— γ -Acetyl- δ -methylcaproic acid (40 g.), prepared by the ketonic hydrolysis of ethyl α -acetyl- α -(β -cyanoethyl)-isovalerate⁷ was esterified azeotropically in benzene solution (8 hours). On working up in the usual way, the ester was obtained as a colorless oil, b. p. 120°/7-8 mm, yield 36g. (80%), n_D^{25} , 1.4285. (Found: C, 65.65; H, 10.50. C₁₁H₂₀O₃ requires C, 66.00; H, 10.00%).

4-Isopropylcyclohexan-1,3-dione (II).—To a well-cooled suspension of ethanol-free sodium ethoxide (prepared from 4.14 g. of sodium) in dry ether (100 ml) was added ethyl γ -acetyl- δ -methylcaproate (I) (35g.) dropwise and with constant stirring. The reaction mixture was initially kept at room temperature for 3 hours and then refluxed for 1 hour when it turned into a solid mass. The solid was decomposed with ice-cold HCl. The organic layer was separated and the aqueous layer extracted four times with ether. The combined extracts were washed with water and dried. After removal of the solvent, the residual oil was vacuum-distilled to furnish a colorless oil, b.p. 156-60°/4 mm, yield 18 g. (67%). The diketone did not give any coloration with ferric chloride solution. (Found: C, 69.83; H, 9.23. C₉H₁₄O₂ requires C, 70.10; H, 9.09%).

2-Isopropyl-5-isobutoxycyclohex-5-enone (III).—A mixture of the diketone (15.4 g.) butanol¹ (40 ml), benzene (150 ml), and *p*-toluenesulphonic acid (0.5 g.) was refluxed under a constant water separator (Dean and Stark type) until no water collected in the limb (6 hours). The reaction mixture was then cooled, the excess of acid was destroyed with a little sodium ethoxide in ethanol, and sufficient amount of water added. The organic layer was separated and the aqueous layer extracted with ether. The combined organic phase was washed with water and dried over sodium sulphate. After removal of the solvent the residual oil was distilled to obtain a colorless oil, b.p. 140-2°/4mm, yield 16.7 g. (79%), n_D^{25} 1.4285. (Found : C, 74.00; H, 10.12. C₁₃H₂₂O₂ requires C, 74.28; H, 10.47%).

4-Isopropylcyclohex-2-enone (IV).—To a suspension of LiAlH₄ (1.1 g.) in anhydrous ether (200 ml) was added 2-isopropyl-5-isobutoxycyclohex-5-enone (16g.) dropwise at a rate so as to maintain ether at a gentle reflux. After the addition was complete the contents were stirred at room temperature for 1 hour. Excess of LiAlH₄ was decomposed at low temperature with cold water (10 ml) and by subsequent addition of ice-cold 10% H₂SO₄ (50 ml). The ethereal layer was separated and the aqueous layer extracted thrice with

4. Frank and Hall, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 1647.

5. Conroy, *ibid.*, 1952, **74**, 3046.

6. Seifert and Schinz, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1951, **34**, 728; Vig and Singh, *this Journal*, 1958, **35**, 715.

7. Misra and Shukla, *this Journal*, 1952, **29**, 201.

*Analysis by Drs. Weiler and Strauss, Oxford.

ether. The combined extracts after washing with dilute solution of sodium bicarbonate and then with water were dried over sodium sulphate. The solvent was removed and the remaining oil distilled to furnish a colorless oil, b. p. $100^{\circ}/2$ mm, yield, 8.3 g. (78.8%), n_D^{20} , 1.4765 (Cahn *et al.*¹ reported for *l*-cryptone n_D^{20} 1.4848); $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{alc}}$ 227 m μ (log ϵ , 3.92) (Cook and Macbeth¹ recorded for *l*-cryptone, $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{alc}}$ 226.3 m μ ; log ϵ , 4.10). (Found: C, 78.01; H, 10.01. Calc. for $C_9H_{14}O$: C, 78.21; H, 10.21%).

The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone was prepared in the usual manner and crystallised from ethyl acetate as orange-red microcrystals, m.p. 130° (Read *et al.*⁸ reported m.p. 132° for the *l*-cryptone derivative). (Found: N, 17.90. Calc. for $C_{15}H_{13}O_4N_4$: N, 17.60%).

The semicarbazone was prepared in the usual way and crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 185° [Cahn *et al.*¹ recorded m.p. 185° (decomp.) for the *l*-cryptone derivative]. (Found: C, 61.22; H, 8.35. Calc. for $C_{10}H_{17}ON_3$: C, 61.53; H, 8.71%).

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Received January 9, 1962.